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Legislative Control of Rulemaking in a Dependent State: A Critical Typology From Brazil

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ABSTRACT

In Brazil, legislative control conditions regulatory agencies' rulemaking through substantive limits, procedural requirements, and ex post review. Drawing on legal analysis and documentary evidence, this article maps these mechanisms through a differentiated framework that combines legislative oversight scholarship, historical institutionalism, Marxist state theory, and Marxist Dependency Theory. It argues that, under dependent capitalism, legislative oversight is not merely a technical correction for bureaucratic drift, but a strategic response to a structural “double pressure”: the need to sustain external credibility while managing domestic legitimacy crises. The result is a critical typology that specifies how distinct legislative coalitions activate material, procedural, and ex post controls. Rather than treating Brazil as an isolated case, the article offers an analytical basis for comparison across regulatory states in the Global South and clarifies the limits of democratic accountability in peripheral economies.

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摘要

在巴西，立法控制通过实质性限制、程序性要求和事后审查来制约监管机构的规则制定。本文运用法律分析和文献证据，构建了一个融合立法监督研究、历史制度主义、马克思主义国家理论和马克思主义依附理论的差异化框架，并以此来阐释这些机制。文章认为，在依附型资本主义体制下，立法监督并非仅仅是对官僚主义倾向的技术性修正，而是对结构性“双重压力”的战略应对：既要维持外部信誉，又要应对国内合法性危机。由此，文章提出了一个重要的类型学，阐明了不同的立法联盟如何激活物质控制、程序控制和事后审查。本文并非将巴西视为孤立案例，而是为比较全球南方各国的监管体系提供了一个分析基础，并阐明了边缘经济体民主问责制的局限性。

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RESUMEN

En Brasil, el control legislativo condiciona la elaboración de normas de las agencias reguladoras mediante límites sustantivos, requisitos procedimentales y una revisión **ex post**. Basándose en el análisis jurídico y en evidencia documental, este artículo cartografía dichos mecanismos a través de un marco diferenciado que combina la literatura sobre la supervisión legislativa, el institucionalismo histórico, la teoría marxista del Estado y la teoría marxista de la dependencia. Se argumenta que, bajo un capitalismo dependiente, la supervisión legislativa no constituye meramente una corrección técnica frente a la deriva burocrática, sino una respuesta estratégica ante una «doble presión» estructural: la necesidad de mantener la credibilidad externa al tiempo que se gestionan las crisis de legitimidad interna. El resultado es una tipología crítica que especifica de qué manera distintas coaliciones legislativas activan controles materiales, procedimentales y **ex post**. En lugar de tratar a Brasil como un caso aislado, el artículo ofrece una base analítica para la comparación entre Estados reguladores del Sur Global y esclarece los límites de la rendición de cuentas democrática en las economías periféricas.

1 | Introduction

Political power is essential to understanding state sovereignty. It unfolds into three functions: legislative, executive, and judicial, secured by functional specialization and organizational independence, thereby forming a concrete division of political power (Silva 2010). By legitimizing and overseeing governmental action, the Legislative Branch exercises auditing and oversight functions. Technical regulation of specific matters is crucial to ensure policies grounded in robust evidence (Clève 2000). Within regulatory economics, policy tools cluster into three spheres: economic regulation, non-economic regulation, and antitrust, each carrying distinct implications for legitimacy, participation, and oversight (Aguilar 2014). In the language of delegation studies, these institutional arrangements formalize a principal–agent relationship in which legislatures delegate authority to specialized agents while seeking to minimize agency loss through statutory design and oversight.

Brazil's regulatory State delegates significant normative authority to specialized agencies whose decisions carry distributive consequences in politically exposed sectors. In mainstream legislative studies, oversight is rarely conceptualized as merely episodic; instead, it is frequently organized as an informational and political system in which monitoring costs are managed through institutional design. In particular, “fire-alarm” arrangements enable outside actors to trigger legislative attention through politically salient signals and formalized channels (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984). Yet, in the Brazilian case, existing accounts still leave underspecified how legislatures structure agencies' rulemaking across the policy cycle: *ex ante* in statutory design, in process through procedural requirements, and *ex post* through review and sanctioning, within a civil-law, presidential system characterized by coalition governance.

This article advances a critical typology of legislative control over agency rulemaking. It distinguishes material control, through which legislatures redefine the substantive scope of delegated authority; procedural control, through which they structure how rulemaking must be produced; and *ex post* control, through which they review, suspend, or politically sanction norms already issued. The Brazilian case is used not merely to classify these modalities, but to explain when and why they are activated in a dependent capitalist setting.

Conceived in the 1990s under the influence of institutional reforms and economic liberalization, Brazilian regulatory agencies were created with a high degree of decision-making autonomy, including normative autonomy, to stabilize technical decisions and insulate them from immediate partisan pressures. That autonomy, however, has always been conditioned by an architecture of control, chiefly legislative, which reserves to Parliament the role of supervising and delimiting the regulatory reach of these entities. In a coalition-presidential setting, legislative power is exercised through specific agents and arenas (committees, party leaders, rapporteurs, coalition brokers, and issue-specific caucuses), so “Congress” cannot be treated as monolithic in empirical analysis (Marques 1997; Figueiredo and Limongi 1998; Santos 2003). Accordingly, the article treats oversight instruments as politically activated mechanisms, whose use depends on venue, actor configuration, and distributive exposure.

For clarity, this article distinguishes “regulamentação” (regulatory rulemaking) from “regulação” (regulation). Following Di Pietro (2010) and Carvalho Filho (2011), regulatory rulemaking refers to infra-legal, normative acts issued by the Executive to complement statutes within their limits; its nature is to concretize and specify legislative commands. By contrast, regulation—according to Majone (2013) and Di Pietro (2010)—encompasses a broader scope, referring to the State's role in organizing, supervising, and enforcing rules in specific sectors of the economy and society. In short, regulatory rulemaking sets the normative framework, while regulation ensures its practical application and compliance.

Within this architecture, agencies' regulatory capacity is limited to what their enabling statutes authorize and to matters that have been “deslegalizadas” (delegified) from law into the regulatory domain. As noted by Diego Neto (2003) and Carvalho Filho (2011), the thesis of delegification holds that the Legislature deliberately transfers specific subjects from the realm of primary legislation to infra-legal rulemaking, expanding agencies' room for normative action and technical discretion. Santos et al. (2022) emphasize that this transfer encompasses regulations, administrative orders, and other secondary or tertiary instruments, allowing for flexibility where complexity and rapid adaptation are required. From a delegation perspective, delegification can be viewed as a statutory design decision that reallocates discretion and policy-making costs, thereby intensifying the need to specify oversight mechanisms and the conditions for activation (Epstein and O'Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002).

Delegation and the resulting normative autonomy raise concerns about accountability, democratic control, and the separation of powers. Transferring competence from the Legislature to agencies heightens the need for effective oversight to ensure adherence to legal and constitutional limits and to the principles of legality, impersonality, morality, publicity, and efficiency (Oliva 2006). In practice, democratic control must translate into substantive boundaries on content, procedural structuring of decision-making, and *ex post* review with the potential for sanctioning. This translates the general problem of agency loss into a concrete institutional agenda: identifying the instruments through which Congress structures rulemaking and the political conditions under which those instruments become operative.

Methodologically, this article is a qualitative, theory-building study based on documentary analysis and structured comparison of illustrative episodes of legislative control over agency rulemaking in Brazil. The documentary corpus includes constitutional provisions, framework statutes, agency-specific legislation, legislative proposals and legislative decree initiatives, parliamentary oversight instruments, selected administrative rulemaking materials, and judicial decisions that redefine the legal boundaries of delegated rulemaking.

Analytically, the framework combines four layers, each with a distinct explanatory role. Principal-agent and legislative oversight scholarship provide the vocabulary for identifying instruments and stages of intervention over delegated rulemaking. Historical institutionalism explains how Brazil's regulatory architecture emerged and why specific oversight channels became available and persisted over time (Steinmo et al. 1992). Marxist state theory qualifies the principal, treating Parliament not as a unitary actor but as a selective and conflict-mediated site shaped by coalitional struggles, class relations, and hegemonic disputes. Marxist Dependency Theory specifies the broader structural setting in which these conflicts unfold, namely a dependent capitalist formation marked by tension between external credibility and domestic legitimacy.

Case selection is purposive rather than exhaustive. Episodes were included when they directly affected the scope, procedure, or review of agency rulemaking, involved an identifiable legislative arena or coalition, and provided sufficient documentary trace to reconstruct the sequence of activation. Among otherwise eligible episodes, analytical priority was given to cases that made more visible the dependency-conditioned tensions central to the article, especially disputes in which legislative intervention mediated between external credibility constraints and domestic distributive or legitimacy pressures. Political activation is therefore inferred not from legislative disagreement in the abstract, but from the observable mobilization of control instruments by identifiable actors in response to concrete regulatory disputes.

The discussion unfolds in three steps: (1) it characterizes the formal and informal mechanisms of parliamentary control over agencies' normative acts; (2) it analyzes how disputes over regulatory autonomy express power relations and class interests; and (3) it situates those disputes within the structural constraints of dependent capitalism. These traditions are mobilized in a differentiated rather than cumulative way to explain how

legislative control over agency rulemaking is institutionally structured, historically sedimented, politically activated, and dependency-conditioned.

Finally, the article is structured into four sections, in addition to this introduction and the concluding remarks. The first presents the creation and institutional evolution of Brazil's regulatory agencies, with emphasis on delegated rulemaking and the thesis of delegation. The second discusses the legal and political foundations of these entities' normative autonomy, including risks associated with bureaucratic self-reference and the limits of democratic accountability. The third section examines the legislative mechanisms of political control over agencies' normative production, based on a documentary review and qualitative analysis of legislative proposals, highlighting concrete examples and their institutional implications. The fourth develops comparative implications and a research agenda, specifying how the typology can be applied beyond Brazil under explicit scope conditions.

2 | Brazil's Regulatory State: Context and Concepts

Building on the problem framing and contributions, this chapter provides the institutional backdrop for Brazil's regulatory agencies. The regulatory function of the Brazilian State is intrinsic to state action itself. It has been constitutionally consolidated since the promulgation of the *Constituição do Brasil de 1988* (Brazil, Federal Constitution of 1988). Article 174 of the Charter establishes that the State is a normative and regulatory agent of economic activity, exercising not only the police power to secure social order but also the power to formulate rules that discipline private activity, especially when it intertwines with the provision of public services (Brazil, Federal Constitution, art. 174 (1988)). The regulatory function is therefore rooted in both the constitutional structure and the historical trajectory of the Brazilian State. From a functional perspective, regulation aims to mitigate information asymmetries, social risks, and adverse cost structures in the public interest (Souto 2002). In delegation terms, this constitutional mandate supplies the institutional ground on which legislatures allocate discretion to specialized agents while retaining instruments to structure, monitor, and correct regulatory outputs under conditions of complexity (Epstein and O'Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002).

2.1 | Comparative Trajectories and Brazil's Reform Turn

The emergence of independent regulatory agencies follows distinct international and sectoral paths. The theory of path dependence (Parente 2008) emphasizes that the unique political-institutional pathways shape design and development. In the United States, the tradition of independent commissions dates back to the late nineteenth century and intensified during the New Deal (1930s), with the establishment of bodies such as the SEC (1934), the FCC (1934), and the NLRB (1935). In post-war Europe (approx. 1945–1970s), state ownership and direct ministerial regulation of public services prevailed; the transition to independent regulators followed the liberalizations and privatizations of the 1980s–1990s (with British precedents and later

EU diffusion in sectors like telecommunications and energy). In Latin America, under import-substitution industrialization (c. 1930–1980), centralized state provision predominated; the creation of independent agencies is a 1990s phenomenon associated with sectoral restructuring and privatization (Aragão 2002). This cross-regional differentiation is not merely chronological; it also signals variation in the political coalitions, credibility problems, and distributive stakes that regulators were expected to manage, thereby conditioning the “baseline” degree of insulation and the typical modes of legislative control (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991).

This divergence frames Brazil’s specific trajectory. In the early 1980s, the international financial crisis and pressure from multilateral organizations led Brazil, like other Latin American countries, to adopt structural adjustment programs inspired by the Washington Consensus. The package—fiscal discipline, spending reorientation, tax reform, trade/financial openness, privatization, deregulation, and property-rights protection—sought to restore external solvency and investment “attractiveness”; in Silva’s (2000) reading, to generate surpluses to service external-debt interest. In Brazil, the agenda deepened under Fernando Collor and Fernando Henrique Cardoso through trade liberalization, divestiture programs, and sectoral restructurings, shifting the State’s role from direct execution to the regulation of economic activities via new institutional architectures.

The mid-1990s state-reform agenda redefined the Brazilian State’s role in the economy. As Barroso (2002) and Araújo (2002) emphasize, constitutional and infra-legal changes facilitated divestiture in strategic sectors, including energy, telecommunications, transportation, and health. In 1996, the Council for State Reform recommended that regulatory agencies serve as instruments of normative coordination, signaling that withdrawal from direct service provision would not entail a retreat from disciplining economic dynamics. According to Farias (2004), unlike the “executive agencies” of the Master Plan—managerial bodies geared to operational efficiency—regulatory agencies were conceived to stabilize the “rules of the game” through delegated rulemaking, providing normative predictability for long-term investment and sectoral oversight. Between 1996 and 2005, ten federal regulatory agencies were created, consolidating this architecture. In Osorio’s (2014) terms, these moves materialized the “mundialization” of the Brazilian State—domestic reform aligned with the dictates of global capital—while, as Piovesan (2009) notes, implementation faced turbulences and shifting power dynamics within the governmental structure. From a legislative-studies standpoint, the reform turn can also be read as a reallocation of discretion under high transaction costs and credibility pressures, in which statutory design and oversight institutions become crucial for containing agency losses while preserving the benefits of specialization (Epstein and O’Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002).

2.2 | Why Agencification: Capacity Gaps, Delegation, and Control

A practical diagnosis also spurred reform: traditional administrative structures proved inadequate for complex sectors

marked by information asymmetries, social risks, and distributive conflicts. Martins (2003) notes deficits in decision-making independence, transparency, procedural celerity, and social participation. In this context, an agencification process institutionalized specialized independent regulators with administrative and financial autonomy and stability for directors (Binenbojm 2008; Mello 2002).

While designed to stabilize technical decisions and insulate them from immediate partisan pressures, agencies’ autonomy has always been conditioned by a political-administrative control architecture—most notably congressional oversight—which reserves to Parliament the power to supervise and delimit these entities’ regulatory reach. A historical-neoinstitutionalist perspective models this as principal-agent delegation: the Legislature (principal) delegates competencies to agencies (agents) to mitigate information asymmetry, opportunism, and credibility-commitment problems (Moe 1984; Bawn 1995). McCubbins et al. (1987) demonstrate that such delegation is accompanied by *ex ante* and *ex post* controls—appointments, conditional budgets, audits, and the possibility of staying regulations—enabling the Legislature to monitor and sanction deviant behavior. The arrangement aims to strike a balance between technical autonomy and political accountability, thereby keeping normative action within legislatively defined bounds.

Two refinements are essential for the argument developed in this article. First, legislative control is often structured as an informational and political system rather than as a continuous “police patrol.” In “fire-alarm” oversight, institutional arrangements empower affected actors to trigger legislative attention and sanctions, reallocating monitoring costs while preserving congressional capacity to intervene when distributive stakes become salient (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984). Second, the choice among control instruments is itself an institutional-design problem: by shaping procedures, venues, and decision rules, legislatures can induce systematic policy outcomes—that is, a structure-induced equilibrium—without direct and constant intervention (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991). These two insights anticipate the typology advanced later in the article, which distinguishes material, procedural, and *ex post* modalities of legislative control over rulemaking.

A critical inflection adds that these controls are traversed by partisan, economic, and ideological logics that reflect class disputes and competing hegemonic projects (Jessop 2015). Credibility concerns also mattered: by shielding regulatory decisions from government turnover, the model aimed to protect contracts, ensure investor confidence, and consolidate a stable regulatory environment (Mello 2002). In this perspective, autonomy is not a “neutral” institutional choice but a politically contested arrangement whose boundaries are periodically recalibrated through legislative venues and instruments. In practice, Brazil moved from initial controversy to institutional pragmatism: agencies were preserved but shaped to reconcile technical autonomy with negotiated political control. In Osorio’s (2014) terms, that recalibration is further conditioned by dependent insertion: the principal’s incentives are altered by structural constraints and coalitional pressures that intensify distributive conflict around regulatory rulemaking.

2.3 | Institutional Design and Core Attributes

Brazilian regulatory agencies follow a distinct legal pattern: as special-status autarchies, they are established by specific statutes and structured as collegial boards with fixed, staggered terms, ensuring stability and autonomy in their decision-making processes. There is no single model (Mattos 2006); in Brazil, agencies combine normative, supervisory, and sanctioning competencies applicable to strategic sectors such as energy, telecommunications, transportation, and health. In light of constitutional provisions and the statutes establishing the agencies—and later baseline governance statutes—Congress has held instruments to condition and redesign regulatory autonomy, at times limiting it, at times reshaping it. This is consistent with statutory-design accounts in which legislatures vary the degree of discretion by calibrating detail, procedures, and review points in response to uncertainty and political conflict (Huber and Shipan 2002; Epstein and O'Halloran 1999).

In operational terms, agencies' regulatory practice encompasses three dimensions: issuing infra-legal norms with coercive force; supervising and overseeing regulated entities; and technically mediating conflicts among users, providers, and the State. This multifunctionality demands technical capacity and institutional mechanisms that secure democratic legitimacy.

Core institutional attributes include: decision-making independence (fixed, non-coincident terms; presidential nomination with Senate confirmation; removal only in specific cases such as administrative impropriety) (Egeberg 2003; McCubbins et al. 1987); financial autonomy derived from autarchic status, reducing budgetary dependence and stabilizing regulatory action (Campos et al. 2000; Marques Neto 2005); administrative autonomy to organize internal processes without hierarchical interference (Garnica and Kempfer 2019); broad publicity and transparency via official publication, public consultations, and access-to-information mechanisms (Campos et al. 2000); stakeholder participation for users, firms, civil society, and experts through formal channels (Marques Neto 2005); and celerity/procedural simplification to keep pace with sectoral dynamics (Campos et al. 2000). From an oversight standpoint, these attributes simultaneously increase the benefits of expertise and raise the political value of control instruments capable of shaping agenda-setting, procedural sequencing, and ex post correction (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991; McCubbins and Schwartz 1984).

2.4 | Political Economy, Endogenous Tensions, and the Bridge to Legal Baselines

These features interacted with Brazil's political economy. Fractions of the domestic bourgeoisie—especially finance, privatized service segments, and export-oriented basic industries—embraced agencies as a way to institutionalize their interests in more stable forms, less susceptible to electoral volatility. This aligns with Jessop's (2007) discussion of preferences for “depoliticized governance,” in which critical decisions are delegated to ostensibly neutral technocratic bodies outside immediate public deliberation. By contrast, fractions of the traditional political class—linked to regional oligarchies, control over state-owned enterprises, or a late national-developmental

agenda—were skeptical or hostile, perceiving that strengthening autonomous agencies threatened historical channels of intermediation and redistribution, shifting decision centers away from day-to-day partisan control. As Osorio (2014) notes, transitions in peripheral states often unfold in a contradictory manner because neoliberal institutional forms must be reconciled with the oligarchic legacies of the patrimonialist State.

In the FHC–Lula transition, however, strategic and selective acceptance prevailed: governance was reconfigured through initiatives such as Bill No. 3337/2004 (early draft of a “general law” on agencies with management contracts, ombuds offices, public hearings, and procedural baselines), professionalization and career measures (Law No. 10,871/2004), and programs to strengthen regulatory capacity and coordination with the Chief of Staff (PRO-REG, Decree No. 6062/2007). Appointments to boards—subject to Senate confirmation—entered coalition bargaining, even as participation and transparency mechanisms expanded. In mainstream delegation terms, these moves can be read as attempts to stabilize commitments while tightening the institutional channels through which principals can structure and correct agency action.

These dynamics generated conflicts over agency autonomy from the model's inception. A historical–institutionalist perspective documents congressional resistance that delayed, conditioned, or reconfigured independence devices—via periodic reporting requirements, fixed terms subject to legislative approval, and clauses enabling the staying of regulations, among others. As Offe (1984) argues, reforms that rationalize public administration along technocratic lines face resistance from coalitions previously advantaged by the normative indeterminacy and decision-making porosity of the traditional apparatus. In Poulantzas's formulation (1977, 2000), the State—here Parliament as its concrete expression—retains relative autonomy to mediate disputes, not as a mere echo of the dominant class but as a structure conditioned by inter- and intra-class struggles. As Jessop (2009) underscores in his re-reading of Poulantzas, relative autonomy does not negate class conditioning; it depends on shifting balances of forces and is exercised through institutionally sedimented selectivities. Parliamentary sectors promoting control mechanisms sought to reconcile neoliberal institutional devices with preexisting power schemas: the aim was not to reject autonomous regulatory logic but to contain it within limits compatible with maintaining legislative influence over policy formation. This is precisely where the article's bridge between delegation studies and dependency theory is located: the principal's incentive to intervene is shaped not only by agency drift but also by the distributive and legitimacy tensions intensified under dependent insertion (Osorio 2014), which heighten the political value of “fire-alarm” activation and of procedural and statutory designs that induce predictable outcomes (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984; Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991).

Since 2019, a consolidated statutory framework has sought to align technical autonomy with democratic control by standardizing appointments and tenure safeguards, mandating participatory procedures and Regulatory Impact Analysis for significant measures, and providing for periodic review of existing norms. The legal baselines thus established frame the next chapter's

analysis of the constitutional foundations and limits of agencies' normative autonomy.

3 | Legal Foundations and Limits of Normative Autonomy: The Legislative Branch in Brazil

Within Brazil's constitutional order, political power is one and indivisible but is exercised through distinct functions—legislative, executive, and judicial—organized by functional specialization and organic (organizational) independence. Separation of powers is thus not a fragmentation of sovereignty, but the legal form through which a single state power is exercised by distinct bodies with autonomous standing, securing the balanced performance of state functions and guarding against the concentration of authority (Silva 2010; Torrens 2013). In this framework, the Legislative Branch—comprising elected members and endowed with representation, legislation, legitimization, oversight, political judgment, and constituent functions—occupies a pivotal position in defining the boundaries of delegated rulemaking and ensuring democratic legitimacy for technocratic decisions. In delegation terms, it is the constitutional locus of the principal, holding authority to allocate discretion by statute and to structure monitoring and sanctioning arrangements that contain agency loss (Epstein and O'Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002).

As established earlier (Section 2), “regulatory rulemaking” refers to the Executive's infra-legal acts that concretize legislative commands, while “regulation” designates the broader functions of organizing, supervising, and enforcing rules in specific sectors (Di Pietro 2010; Carvalho Filho 2011). The discussion that follows draws on this distinction to show that normative autonomy is not a generic attribute of agencies but a derivative, legally bounded competence structured by statutory design, procedures, and review points. Brazilian administrative law frequently grounds such intervention in a doctrine of institutional deference to specialized regulators, provided statutory and constitutional limits are respected (Fonseca 2014). From the perspective of legislative oversight, deference does not eliminate control; rather, it heightens the importance of ex ante statutory constraints, procedural design (“deck-stacking”), and ex post review to ensure that delegated rulemaking remains within the legally authorized policy space (McCubbins et al. 1987; Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991).

3.1 | The General Law of Regulatory Agencies (Law No. 13,848/2019)

Law No. 13,848/2019 (GLRA/2019) systematizes the governance, decision-making, and accountability framework applicable to Brazil's federal regulatory agencies. It combines organizational safeguards (eligibility and incompatibilities for directors, fixed terms, post-term cooling-off) with procedural requirements that structure rulemaking, aligning technical autonomy with democratic control. Specifically, GLRA/2019 mandates a forward-looking regulatory agenda and participatory procedures (including public hearings and consultations), requires Regulatory Impact Analysis for significant measures, and provides for periodic review of the existing normative

framework; together, these instruments broaden vertical and horizontal accountability and embed checks and balances in the regulatory process. In mainstream terms, these devices operate as ex ante and in-process controls: they structure the decision-making sequence, increase transparency and contestability, and reduce informational asymmetries that otherwise constrain principals' capacity to monitor agents (McCubbins et al. 1987; Huber and Shipan 2002).

The statute sets minimum eligibility criteria for directors, prohibits the appointment of sitting political and party officials, standardizes fixed terms, and establishes a cooling-off period after service, aiming to reduce direct partisan influence while preserving accountability to the elected branches. It requires agencies to adopt regulatory planning, conduct public hearings and consultations, and provide reason-giving in decisions, formalizing opportunities for societal and market input and increasing transparency and contestability. Regulatory quality is strengthened through the RIA for significant measures and periodic review to assess coherence, necessity, and proportionality, thereby preventing self-referential regulation and ensuring that infra-legal acts are consistent with statutory mandates. By mandating ex-ante analysis, participation, and ex-post evaluation, the statute reaffirms that an agency's normative autonomy is derivative of the statute and subject to ongoing oversight. Procedural requirements of this sort can be understood as “deck-stacking” strategies: by shaping who participates, what information is produced, and how reasons must be articulated, legislatures can channel regulatory outputs toward predictable policy equilibria without constant intervention (McCubbins et al. 1987; Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991). Debates over the presidential veto of shortlists for director appointments highlight persistent tensions between technical autonomy and political control: the absence of a shortlist does not, by itself, compromise independence (Costa et al. 2021; Miranda et al. 2021), but it signals structural limits to insulating appointments from political orientation. The Law's effectiveness, therefore, depends on both formal compliance and an institutional culture oriented toward integrity, predictability, and public participation.

3.2 | Constitutional and Parliamentary Instruments of Control

Among the constitutional instruments of legislative control, notable examples include parliamentary inquiry commissions; summoning agency heads to provide explanations; formal information requests to indirect-administration bodies (art. 50, Federal Constitution); and, especially, the power to stay normative acts that exceed regulatory authority (art. 49(V), Federal Constitution). Budgetary control, Senate confirmation of nominees to directorships, and public hearings—where society and representatives can assess coherence, impacts, and pertinence of regulatory decisions—complement these tools. Together, these actions compose “expanded accountability” (Scott 2000), encompassing both the obligation to inform and justify and the concrete possibility of sanction (cf. Mainwaring 1997). GLRA/2019 advances the institutionalization of control and transparency, maintaining normative activity under sustained parliamentary and public oversight. From the standpoint of oversight theory, these instruments also vary in monitoring cost and activation logic: some resemble “police-patrol”

mechanisms centered on direct legislative surveillance, while others operate as “fire-alarms,” enabling affected actors, media, and organized interests to trigger legislative attention through institutionalized channels (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984).

Implementation, however, faces structural hurdles, including information asymmetries, limited qualified participation by segments of civil society, pressure from organized economic groups, and political influence over appointments, which curtail the reach of democratic control (Costa et al. 2021). The legislative process itself is constrained by Executive tools such as provisional measures and vetoes, which can weaken the Legislature’s oversight role (Fix-Zamudio 1994). Precisely under these constraints, the design of oversight channels becomes consequential. When monitoring is costly, legislatures tend to rely more heavily on institutional arrangements that externalize detection costs and concentrate intervention on high-salience disputes. This logic is consistent with the fire-alarm model, in which oversight capacity depends less on constant monitoring and more on the availability of credible triggers and sanctioning tools (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984). Precisely for this reason, parliamentary control becomes all the more necessary to secure compliance with institutional limits and safeguard the public interest when regulatory decisions risk exceeding legally assigned purposes.

3.3 | Delegation, Legal Bases, and Accountability Architecture

The legal basis for agencies’ regulatory action rests on the thesis of delegification (deslegalização), as theorized by Diego Neto (2003) and supported by Carvalho Filho (2011). This doctrine authorizes the Legislature to transfer matters traditionally governed by formal statutes to the infra-legal domain when technical complexity or the need for frequent updates justifies delegation, thereby broadening the normative latitude of agencies in terms of specialization and efficiency. As Santos et al. (2022) emphasize, this transfer—via regulations, administrative orders, and other secondary or tertiary instruments—poses legal challenges, as shifting the normative centrality from Parliament to administrative entities requires guarantees of legality, proportionality, and transparency in regulatory acts. In broader terms, this problem reflects the transformation of lawmaking in the administrative state, where binding legal norms are increasingly produced through administrative rulemaking rather than exclusively through statutes enacted by legislatures (Rubin 1989). Even when grounded in statutory delegation, an agency’s normative action cannot exceed constitutional limits and remains subject to judicial review and parliamentary control.

In delegation and statutory-design accounts, delegification is best understood as a legislative choice to allocate discretion in the face of uncertainty and transaction costs. Legislatures can respond by calibrating statutory detail, procedural requirements, and review points to contain agency loss while preserving the gains from specialization (Epstein and O’Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002). By shaping procedures and decision rules, legislatures can induce systematic outcomes—a structure-induced equilibrium—rather than relying exclusively on episodic interventions (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991). This architecture operationalizes accountability beyond mere transparency.

3.4 | Analytical Lenses: Institutional Checks and Political Economy of Oversight

From a classical institutional perspective, legislative interference functions as a check-and-balance device to prevent abuses and correct course when an agency exceeds its technical mandate. A critical lens suggests that the “principal’s interests” are themselves shaped by social power relations: control mechanisms are traversed by partisan, economic, and ideological logics that reflect class disputes and competing hegemonic projects (Marques 1997; Jessop 2015; Offe 1984, 1975). The agencies’ design—directors nominated by the President and confirmed by the Senate—lays bare the intrinsic political dimension of their action; decision-making independence has never been absolute but is conditioned by appointment arrangements and subject to prevailing power correlations and politico-economic coalitions.

The key theoretical move is therefore not to reject principal-agent logic, but to endogenize the principal. Oversight scholarship identifies the available instruments of control, but it does not by itself explain why particular arenas and coalitions activate them at specific moments. In Poulantzas’s formulation (1977, 2000), the State is a material condensation of relations of force among classes and fractions; autonomy is relative and exercised within those limits. Gramsci’s notion of hegemonic struggle helps show how technical-administrative bodies become arenas in which rival projects of power and legitimacy contest direction (Gramsci 1988). In contexts of dependent capitalism (Osorio 2014), these tensions intensify under a double pressure: maintaining the confidence of transnational capital and its domestic allies while responding to social demands and legitimacy crises linked to peripheral insertion. In such settings, oversight cannot be reduced to the prevention of drift; it also functions as a recurrent instrument through which coalitions activate available controls to manage distributive conflict and legitimacy stress. These legal and political bases inform the three modalities analyzed below.

4 | Political Control Over Agencies’ Rulemaking in Brazil: A Critical Typology

This chapter applies the typology to purposively selected episodes of legislative control over delegated rulemaking in Brazil, tracing the actors, arenas, instruments, and distributive stakes through which each modality becomes operative.

The discussion is organized by modality. Each subsection clarifies the specific logic of material, procedural, or ex post control and then examines illustrative episodes in terms of trigger, arena, coalition, instrument, and regulatory consequence.

4.1 | Material Legislative Control: Substantive Limits on Rulemaking

Material control concerns legislative interventions that redefine the legally authorized content, scope, or outer boundary of agency rulemaking. It operates at the level of delegated authority itself: instead of merely reacting to a specific normative

act, Congress may expand, narrow, reorder, or harden the substantive parameters within which agencies may regulate. Such intervention can occur through amendments to enabling statutes, framework legislation, constitutional change, or statutory provisions that fix distributive baselines and remove matters from infra-legal discretion (Spiller et al. 2003). From a statutory-design standpoint, material control is the clearest way for principals to recalibrate delegated authority under conditions of uncertainty, distributive conflict, or heightened political exposure (Huber and Shipan 2002; Epstein and O'Halloran 1999).

The key analytical point is that material control acts on what agencies may normatively decide, not merely on how they decide or on how their decisions are later reviewed. Legislative delegation may therefore be broad, conditional, or highly restricted, depending on whether Congress prefers to entrust agencies with open-ended technical discretion, bind them to specific statutory parameters, or reserve politically sensitive choices to primary legislation. In this sense, material control often becomes a form of “policymaking by statute”: it locks in distributive settlements in law, narrows the space for infra-legal experimentation, and makes visible the political coalitions that seek to stabilize or recalibrate regulatory authority.

The contestation over the “General Law” and the Executive’s PL n° 3.337/2004 illustrates material control at the meta-institutional level: rather than revising a single agency decision, coalitions disputed the statutory architecture governing multiple agencies. *Trigger*: executive dissatisfaction with insulated autonomy devices; *arena*: comprehensive statutory reform proposal; *coalition*: executive leadership versus a parliamentary coalition organized through a pro-agency front; *instrument*: PL n° 3.337/2004 met by counter-mobilization and a constitutional move via PEC n° 81/2003 (Nunes et al. 2007; Brazil, Projeto de Lei n° 3.337/2004; Brazil, PEC n° 81/2003). This episode matters analytically because it shows that “material control” includes not only sectoral statutes but also cross-cutting institutional baselines that redefine autonomy and accountability for the regulatory state as a whole.

In the regulation of human plasma, although the topic falls within ANVISA’s scope, Article 199, §4 of the Federal Constitution prohibits the commercialization of human organs, tissues, and substances. However great ANVISA’s technical competence to regulate operational aspects, it cannot contravene the constitutional rule by authorizing sales. The Proposed Constitutional Amendment No. 10/2022, if approved, would alter this material limit; ANVISA would then regulate the new collection and commercialization processes, still bound by the amended constitutional framework.

Analogous to the plasma case in health regulation, the power sector offers a paradigmatic instance of material legislative interference that reshapes an agency’s normative remit. ANEEL’s Normative Resolution No. 482/2012 established the net-metering scheme for distributed micro- and mini-generation, and it long functioned as the infra-legal backbone of this arrangement. After intense sectoral and parliamentary debate, Congress enacted Law No. 14,300/2022 (Distributed Generation Legal Framework), which codified core elements previously located in ANEEL’s infra-legal regulation, without repealing RN No. 482/2012, now repositioned as a subordinate instrument detailing the statute. By

fixing in law parameters for compensation, eligibility, and transition, the Legislature narrowed ANEEL’s discretion on typified matters and converted a previously infra-legal arrangement into a statute-centered distributive settlement. The episode therefore exemplifies material control: Parliament redefines the substance and limits of rulemaking with systemic effects on predictability and on the allocation of costs and benefits among market participants. In statutory-design terms, the shift from infra-legal calibration to codification reflects a deliberate reallocation of discretion and a move to lock in distributive terms by statute (Huber and Shipan 2002).

In the aftermath of the 2018 truckers’ strike, the Executive issued Provisional Measure No. 832/2018, and Congress subsequently enacted Law No. 13,703/2018, establishing the National Policy on Minimum Freight Floors for road cargo transport. The statute mandated ANTT to publish a minimum-freight table and to update it semiannually, thereby enshrining in law informal design choices and narrowing the agency’s discretion over the policy’s core parameters. ANTT immediately operationalized the regime through Resolution No. 5820/2018, with subsequent revisions scheduled under the legal framework. As in the electricity case, this episode exemplifies material legislative control: Parliament sets the substantive content and temporal cadence of the policy, with ANTT confined to technical detailing and enforcement within legislatively fixed boundaries. This pattern is consistent with the logic of constraining discretion where distributive stakes and political costs are high and recurrent.

By enacting Law No. 14,026/2020, Congress expanded ANA’s mandate to issue reference norms for public sanitation services and linked federal transfers and program eligibility to compliance with the statute’s institutional architecture (e.g., regionalized service blocks and adherence to federal standards). In doing so, the Legislature reconfigured the agency’s competence and embedded financial conditionality to steer subnational implementation. This is a clear instance of material control: it not only delimits ANA’s infra-legal space, but also channels its normative activity through statute-defined objectives and incentives. ANA’s room for rulemaking is therefore exercised within legislative design choices that bind the content, scope, and effectiveness of its reference norms.

In the field of pesticides, Law No. 14,785/2023 repeals the prior regime (Laws No. 7802/1989 and 9974/2000). It redistributes competences, narrowing infra-legal discretion by tying decisions to a juristic–technical concept whose operative content remains to be regulated. ANVISA’s updating of toxicological guidelines evidences adaptive movement, while segments of the public health and environmental sciences communities point to protective backsliding and power asymmetries favoring the productive sector, characterizing the statute as a high-impact regulatory rollback for public and ecological health. Here, material control operates as a high-leverage intervention: it restructures competence allocations and resets the baseline for infra-legal risk governance.

In pharmaceutical advertising, Law No. 9294/1996 provides the statutory baseline. The Superior Court of Justice, in Special Appeal 2,035,645/DF (2024), held that ANVISA exceeded its competence by imposing advertising restrictions not provided for in the statute, judicially narrowing sanitary normative

autonomy, and binding the agency to a statutory minimum script. From the vantage point of regulatory-state theory, this recalibration internalizes the key to protective advances in Parliament. It may chill infra-legal initiatives aimed at precaution and consumer–patient protection.

A closely related boundary case concerns legislative attempts to override sanitary risk controls in the pharmaceutical industry. Congress enacted Law No. 13,454/2017, authorizing the marketing of certain appetite suppressants notwithstanding ANVISA's restrictive stance in RDC No. 52/2011. The Brazilian Supreme Federal Court later struck down the statute in ADI 5779 (2021), reaffirming that material limits grounded in constitutional health protection cannot be bypassed by ordinary legislation. Earlier, the Court invalidated Law No. 13,269/2016, which had authorized the distribution of synthetic phosphoethanolamine without regular regulatory approval, in ADI 5501 (2020). These rulings illustrate a hard material constraint on parliamentary redesigns of the regulatory domain: when legislation seeks to legislate around evidence-based sanitary safeguards, constitutional review restores the baseline within which agencies exercise their technical remit.

Material interference juxtaposes technical rationality with immediate political rationality. It can reflect pressure from organized interests to crystallize privileges in statute, legalizing private advantages as universal, or it can respond tactically to popular demands on high-salience issues, making Parliament an arena that contests any technocratic monopoly over expertise. In dependent capitalism, these tensions intensify because legal frameworks mediate between external constraints and internal needs for legitimation (Marini 1973; Osorio 2014; Santos 1978). In delegation terms, this is the point at which principals substitute statutory codification for bureaucratic discretion when legitimacy stress, distributive conflict, or coalition pressures make “hands-off” autonomy politically costly.

4.2 | Procedural Legislative Control: Decision-Making Requirements

Procedural control concerns legislative interventions that structure the path through which agencies produce norms. Unlike material control, which redefines the substantive perimeter of delegated authority, procedural control acts on the decision-making sequence itself: who must be heard, what information must be produced, which justificatory burdens must be met, and under what formal steps a rule may validly emerge. It therefore operates at the second level of the regulatory framework (Spiller et al. 2003), shaping not the immediate content of the rule in the first instance, but the institutional conditions under which that content may be formulated. Requirements such as Regulatory Impact Analysis, public hearings and consultations, inclusion in regulatory agendas, and reason-giving duties function as institutional counterweights to technical autonomy and were consolidated in Brazil by Law No. 13,848/2019 (Guerra and Salinas 2018).

The evidence also supports a critical refinement: procedural politics is not reducible to “formal legal requirements,” because identifiable caucuses and stakeholders can strategically

organize arenas of hearing, consultation, and information selection. A paradigmatic illustration—although centered on legislative deliberation around a federal measure—is the trajectory of MP 415/2008 (later Law No. 11,705/2008, “Lei Seca”). Trigger: restrictions on alcohol sales near federal highways; arena: a public hearing convened by an issue-specific caucus (Frente Parlamentar em Defesa do Trânsito Seguro—FPDTS) on 26 March 2008; coalition: sectors of commerce, food services, and hospitality mobilizing to soften restrictions; instrument: a package of proposed amendments, many aimed at flexibilization, alongside the notable absence of health-sector representation in the deliberative venue (Lima 2008; Machado 2011). Analytically, this episode helps specify how “fire-alarm” dynamics and venue choice can shape what counts as relevant evidence and whose preferences are internalized in policy design. This logic is directly transferable to understanding how procedural requirements in rulemaking may be activated, contested, or strategically complied with.

In Public Consultation No. 18/2023, the National Petroleum Agency (ANP) reopened the methodology for the oil reference price (PRP)—the basis for royalties/participations—proposing changes to Resolution ANP No. 874/2022 and setting new vacatio/transitional periods. The consultation page and docket materials record the proceeding and its objective (revising PRP criteria). In the ensuing debate, a UFRJ analytical report highlighted that ANP modified the draft but did not conduct a new RIA, prompting concerns about legality, given Law No. 13,848/2019, Article 6, which requires a prior RIA for the issuance, amendment, or repeal of general-interest norms. The duty to conduct RIA and consultations is also reaffirmed on agencies' own governance pages and by Decree No. 10,411/2020, which details the content of RIA and the limited grounds for dispensation. Taken together, the episode illustrates procedural legislative control: Parliament binds infra-legal rulemaking to formalized procedures (RIA plus consultation/hearing), and when those rites are not observed after material changes, legitimacy and legal-certainty critiques follow. The analytical point is not merely that agency discretion is bounded in the abstract, but that procedure itself becomes a site through which external actors can trigger scrutiny and potential political response by pointing to procedural noncompliance—a paradigmatic “fire-alarm” dynamic that reallocates monitoring costs away from continuous congressional surveillance (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984).

Ambivalence is inherent. Employed sparingly and clearly, procedural requirements foster transparency, predictability, and qualified participation; instrumentalized by corporate interests or conjunctural pressures, they can obstruct effective regulation and enable capture. In practice, sectoral caucuses and Executive actors mobilize procedural architecture to recalibrate the limits of agency action. A Gramscian reading sees Law as a trench in a war of position, juridically codifying gains and blocking advances by subaltern forces (Gramsci 1988), echoing Poulantzas's account of the materiality of the legal apparatus. Domestically, the 2019 statute aligned Brazil with the international repertoire of “regulatory quality/governance” (RIA), encompassing participation, transparency, ex post evaluation, and stock review, while anchoring autonomy in a framework of due process and impact measurement. This reframing tends to depoliticize distributive

conflicts by converting them into tests of methodological conformity—RIA scopes, cost–benefit matrices, and evidentiary standards—opening asymmetries between well-organized sectors and diffuse publics, particularly acute in dependent economies (Osorio 2014). In terms of structure-induced equilibrium, procedural rules can stabilize predictable outputs, but the distribution of participatory capacity shapes who can effectively use these channels (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991).

4.3 | Ex Post Review: Parliamentary Oversight and Sanctions

Ex post control concerns legislative interventions that occur after an agency has already issued a normative act. Unlike material control, which resets the scope of delegated authority, and procedural control, which structures the path of rulemaking, ex post review is retrospective: it seeks to scrutinize, suspend, correct, politically sanction, or otherwise discipline norms once they enter the legal and political field. In Brazil, its constitutional anchor lies in Article 49(V) of the Federal Constitution, which grants Congress competence to stay Executive acts that exceed regulatory authority—a power that extends to regulatory agencies. In practice, Legislative Decree Bills (Projetos de Decreto Legislativo, PDLs), hearings, summons, budgetary pressure, and reputational sanction all compose this modality of control, even when formal annulment is not ultimately carried out (Guerra and Salinas 2018).

The analytical importance of ex post control is that it turns retrospective review into a credible political threat. Once a rule produces distributive effects, mobilizes organized interests, or generates legitimacy costs, legislative actors may react by reopening the issue in parliamentary arenas and by activating sanctioning instruments against the agency or its norm. In oversight theory, this is the moment at which ex ante and procedural constraints acquire practical force because the possibility of subsequent correction disciplines delegated rulemaking even in the absence of constant surveillance. Ex post review therefore lies at the intersection of legality and politics: it can serve democratic correction, but it can also operate as a mechanism through which powerful coalitions reassert primacy over technically grounded decisions.

There is evidence that ex post oversight is not merely a constitutional abstraction but a politically mobilizable instrument clustered around salient distributive conflicts. The Paraquat controversy is exemplary. Trigger: ANVISA's ban and subsequent flexibilization trajectory concerning Paraquat (RDC No. 177/2017; later changes culminating in RDC No. 428/2020); arena: simultaneous activation of agency decision-making arenas and congressional ex post instruments; coalition: regulated actors and allied parliamentary networks, with explicit support from the Frente Parlamentar da Agropecuária (FPA); instrument: a concentrated set of PDL initiatives seeking to suspend the RDCs, alongside broader political pressure on agency governance and appointments (Repórter Brasil 2020; Bruno 2021; Walendorff 2020). The pattern is analytically essential for two reasons. First, it documents how ex post control can be used as a sanctioning threat and a reputational lever, even when formal suspension is not carried out. Second, it clarifies how “fire

alarms” operate in practice: affected constituencies and organized interests elevate conflicts to legislative arenas, making retrospective sanction a viable political response (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984).

Although the focus here is on parliamentary ex post control, ultimate constitutional review circumscribes legislative interventions that destabilize evidence-based regulatory baselines. The Supreme Federal Court's annulment of Law No. 13,269/2016 (ADI 5501, 2020) and Law No. 13,454/2017 (ADI 5779, 2021) signals that even politically responsive recalibrations of agency authority remain bounded by constitutional commitments to health protection and due process in risk regulation.

In the pharmaceutical risk area, this triangle of actors—Parliament, regulators, and courts—produces a layered constraint: RDC No. 52/2011 expresses the agency's technical assessment; statutes such as Law No. 13,454/2017 express political recalibration; and constitutional adjudication, as in ADI 5779, sets the outer legal limit. Ex post oversight thus operates within a constitutional envelope that both enables and restrains legislative control.

Ex post oversight also includes “police patrol” devices designed to institutionalize routine accountability. The Senate's Resolution No. 4/2013, mandating annual appearances of regulatory agency heads, is a salient example of formalized, continuous oversight that lowers informational barriers for legislators and creates a recurring venue for contestation, justification, and reputational sanction (Brazil, Senate Resolution No. 4/2013; da Silva 2013). Such instruments matter because they structure oversight temporality (periodic rather than episodic) and reduce monitoring costs by regularizing information flows.

The main instruments include Parliamentary Commissions of Inquiry, summoning agency leaders to provide explanations, periodic public hearings such as those offered by Senate Resolution No. 4/2013, rejection of nominations or reconfirmations of regulatory directors, amendments to enabling statutes as an indirect sanction, and budgetary pressure or symbolic reprimand capable of inducing moderation or acceleration of regulatory action. Effective use requires striking a balance between respecting technical autonomy and the demands of democratic conformity; otherwise, regulatory stability and legal certainty are undermined.

4.4 | Comparative Implications and Research Agenda

The bridge to mainstream oversight is not one of replacement but of specification. Statutory constraints, procedural design, and ex post sanctions can be understood as institutional channels through which coalitional conflicts and dependency-conditioned legitimacy pressures are translated into control over delegated rulemaking. In this sense, legislative control works both as a mechanism of accountability and as a site of distributive struggle: “fire-alarms” lower monitoring costs and concentrate attention on salient conflicts (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984), while procedural and statutory rules can

induce predictable outcomes by shaping arenas and decision rules (Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991; McCubbins et al. 1987). What the Brazilian evidence adds is that activation is frequently traceable to specific legislative arenas and coalition entrepreneurs (fronts, special commissions, issue caucuses) whose incentives are structured by the distributive exposure of regulatory decisions and by the contradictions of dependent capitalism.

Although this article develops its typology from Brazil, its ambition is not to treat Brazil as *sui generis*, but to specify observable forms of legislative control over delegated rulemaking that can be traced across regulatory states. This comparative logic is synthesized in Table 1, which summarizes the three modalities of legislative control, their main instruments, illustrative examples, and implications for autonomy and accountability.

The typology's comparative leverage rests on a stage-sensitive claim widely recognized in delegation and oversight research: legislatures can influence agencies "ex ante" through statutory scope conditions and competence design, "in process" through procedural constraints that structure information, participation, and the decision path, and "ex post" through review and sanctioning instruments (McCubbins et al. 1987; Kiewiet and McCubbins 1991; Huber and Shipan 2002). This ordering clarifies how legislatures shape not only the content of regulatory outcomes but also the pathways by which agencies produce norms, and how they may retrospectively correct, block, or reauthorize agency action. It also facilitates comparison across institutional contexts in which the relative weight of each stage differs: some systems rely heavily on statutory detail and jurisdictional allocation (Huber and Shipan 2002), others emphasize proceduralization as a substitute for continuous monitoring (McCubbins et al. 1987), and still others lean on ex post levers—veto threats, annulment initiatives, or budgetary sanctions—to discipline rulemaking (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984).

A second comparative implication concerns scope conditions: the Brazilian evidence suggests that the incentives to activate oversight cannot be derived solely from institutional design. Principal-agent and transaction-cost delegation models clarify the available instruments—statutory detail, discretion, and monitoring—but tend to bracket the political-economic determinants of what counts as 'agency loss' and when legislators find intervention worth its transaction costs (Epstein and O'Halloran 1999; Huber and Shipan 2002). In dependent settings, those determinants are structured by the credibility–distribution double pressure discussed above: oversight becomes more likely when rulemaking concentrates visible distributive costs or undermines accepted baselines of protection, and it can also be used to entrench permissive equilibria when dominant coalitions benefit from blocking protective innovation (Marini 1973; Osorio 2014; Santos 1978).

A third implication concerns comparative trajectory and, in particular, the politics of "late agencification." Scholarship on the rise of the regulatory state emphasizes that independent regulatory agencies diffused unevenly across time, sectors, and regions, and that their diffusion is tied to transformations in capitalism and governance (Majone 1994, 1997; Levi-Faur 2005). In Western Europe, the spread of independent regulatory agencies

is commonly linked to concerns about policy credibility, liberalization, and delegation strategies, producing cross-national variation in timing and institutional forms (Gilardi 2002; Thatcher 2002; Gilardi 2005). In Latin America, the diffusion of autonomous regulators is strongly associated with state restructuring, privatization, and sectoral reforms, with observable cross-country and cross-sector patterns of adoption and redesign (Jordana and Levi-Faur 2004; Jordana and Levi-Faur 2005). In much of the Global South, the rise of regulators in infrastructure sectors is similarly tied to development constraints, donor and investor expectations, and the politics of distribution in network industries (Dubash and Morgan 2013). These different origins matter because they shape baseline expectations about insulation, autonomy, and the normalcy of political correction. Where agencification is late and linked to externally oriented credibility projects, statutory baselines may be more contested, proceduralization may be uneven or strategically deployed, and ex post interventions may become a recurrent modality of reasserting political primacy during distributive crises (Levy and Spiller 1996; Jordana and Levi-Faur 2004; Dubash and Morgan 2013).

The typology summarized in Table 1 can therefore be used as an analytical scheme for structuring comparisons across dependent or semi-peripheral cases without requiring an immediate large-N design. In Latin America, research on utilities and network sectors documents recurring tensions between voter-facing distributive demands and investor-facing credibility constraints—precisely the double pressure highlighted by dependency approaches—and shows how political competition and coalition incentives shape regulatory outcomes and institutional redesign (Murillo 2009). In Argentina, for example, work on the institutional foundations of policymaking underscores how shifting political bargains and credibility problems condition the stability of regulatory commitments and invite recurrent renegotiation (Spiller and Tommasi 2007). Comparative political economy research on regulatory commitment further demonstrates how institutional and political configurations shape the credibility and durability of regulation in settings with contested commitment and distributive exposure (Levy and Spiller 1996). In India, South Africa, and other emerging economies, the infrastructure-focused literature highlights that regulators operate under intense distributive pressures (tariffs, access, cross-subsidies) and that the "regulatory state of the South" often combines formal adoption of global governance templates with highly politicized arenas of contestation and recalibration (Dubash and Morgan 2013). These cases are not invoked to claim equivalence with Brazil, but to show how the Brazilian typology can be applied elsewhere by coding modalities of control (material, procedural, ex post) and tracing activation sequences, rather than treating "interference" as an undifferentiated residual.

Researchers describe recurrent episodes in which tariff policy and concession rules become electorally salient and trigger political recalibration under credibility–distribution tensions (Levy and Spiller 1996; Murillo 2009). Applying the present scheme, episodes of statutory redesign of tariff/indexation principles or competence reallocations would be coded as material control, expansions or strategic deployment of rulemaking procedures (hearings, reporting duties, periodic review) as procedural control, and post hoc interventions—investigative hearings, summons, budgetary pressure, or formal initiatives aimed at suspension/annulment—as

TABLE 1 | Legislative strategies of control over regulatory agencies' rulemaking: A comparative typology.

Modality of legislative control and principal-agent logic	Main instruments	Illustrative examples & Key actors	Implications for autonomy and accountability
<p>Material (Substantive limits on rulemaking)</p> <p>Defines scope/content; functions as an ex ante statutory constraint to solve credibility problems or settle distributive conflicts by removing discretion.</p>	<p>Constitutional amendments;</p> <p>framework statutes;</p> <p>detailed statutory parameters that “tie” regulatory content to legal standards.</p>	<p>Brazil: The Agribusiness Front (FPA) secured Law No. 14,785/2023, which redistributes competence away from ANVISA regarding pesticides.</p> <p>Brazil: The solar lobby pushed Law No. 14,300/2022 to codify net-metering benefits, removing ANEEL's discretion.</p> <p>Argentina: Use of “Public Emergency Laws” (post-2001) to freeze utility tariffs and override regulatory contracts, establishing a statutory regime of “social affordability”.</p> <p>Mexico: Statutory reversals (LIE) to re-center state control over private generation, limiting the regulator's (CRE) market design powers.</p>	<p>Replaces technical discretion with statutory rigidity (“policy making by statute”); locks in distributive gains for specific legislative coalitions; replaces technocratic insulation with political redistribution during crises.</p>
<p>Procedural (Decision-making requirements)</p> <p>Structures the decision path; operates as “deck-stacking” to bias outcomes by shaping information flows and participation rules.</p>	<p>Regulatory Impact Analysis (RIA); Public hearings/consultations;</p> <p>Reason-giving duties.</p>	<p>Brazil: The Traffic Safety Front used public hearings on “Lei Seca” to mobilize against commerce sectors.</p> <p>Brazil: Stakeholders used the lack of a new RIA (Law 13,848/2019) as a procedural veto point to challenge ANP's oil price methodology.</p> <p>South Africa: Public hearings on electricity tariffs (NERSA/Eskom) function as the primary arena for managing social unrest, often delaying technical adjustments.</p> <p>India: “Consultation Papers” by the telecom regulator (TRAI) are strategically used to delay decisions or signal policy preference in contested disputes.</p>	<p>Increases transparency but allows well-organized groups to exercise vetoes via procedural non-compliance claims; translates distributive conflict into methodological disputes; serves as a “safety valve” for social pressure.</p>
<p>Ex Post (Parliamentary oversight and sanctions)</p> <p>Reviews, stays, or pressures after norms are issued; acts as a “fire-alarm” response to legitimacy crises.</p>	<p>Legislative Decree Bills (PDLs); CPIs; Summons;</p> <p>Budgetary pressure;</p> <p>Confirmation leverage.</p>	<p>Brazil: The Agribusiness Front (FPA) activated PDLs to suspend ANVISA bans on Paraquat, acting as a “fire-alarm” for the sector.</p> <p>Brazil: Annual hearings (Senate Res. 4/2013) function as “police patrol” to reduce informational asymmetries.</p> <p>Argentina: Recurrent executive/legislative “Interventions” in regulatory bodies (ENRE/ENARGAS) with removal of directors during economic crises.</p> <p>Global South: Frequent use of ad-hoc legislative scrutiny to halt tariff hikes that threaten political stability (Dubash and Morgan 2013).</p>	<p>Conditions <i>de facto</i> independence on political support; ensures political responsiveness when technocratic decisions impose high social costs; risks regulatory instability but prevents “bureaucratic drift” away from the power bloc's interests.</p>

Abbreviations: ANEEL, Brazilian Electricity Regulatory Agency; ANP, National Agency of Petroleum; ANVISA, Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency; CRE, Energy Regulatory Commission (Mexico); FPA, Agribusiness Parliamentary Front; NERSA, National Energy Regulator of South Africa; PDL, Legislative Decree Bill; RIA, Regulatory Impact Analysis; TRAI, Telecom Regulatory Authority of India.

ex post control (McCubbins and Schwartz 1984; Bawn 1995). Crucially, the ‘endogenized principal’ element travels in the coding: activation is traced to specific venues and coalition configurations (committee jurisdictions, party leadership, coalition brokers, sectoral legislative entrepreneurs), whose incentives depend on whether regulation threatens voter-facing distributive commitments or investor-facing credibility projects (Murillo 2009; Spiller and Tommasi 2007). This brief illustration is not offered as new evidence, but as a demonstration of how the typology can be operationalized outside Brazil.

Building on these comparative implications, the typology supports testable hypotheses for future research:

- H1 (distributive exposure): The probability of legislative activation increases with the visibility and concentration of distributive stakes generated by agency rulemaking; high-salience sectors should exhibit more frequent activation than low-salience technical domains.
- H2 (coalitional configuration): Control modalities vary with the legislative venues and coalitions that can credibly threaten agenda obstruction or deliver majorities; where coalition brokers and issue-specific caucuses dominate, statutory redesign should be more common than purely procedural steering.
- H3 (legitimacy stress): In contexts where technocratic legitimacy is comparatively fragile, ex post correction should be more frequent following episodes of social contestation, price shocks, or perceived regulatory overreach, and may be activated through “fire-alarm” pathways that shift monitoring costs onto affected constituencies.
- H4 (credibility regime and proceduralization): Where agencies are embedded in investor-facing credibility strategies, procedural controls may be expanded to signal regulatory quality. Still, their effective operation will depend on the distribution of organizational capacity across societal actors.

Methodologically, these hypotheses can be examined through structured within-case comparisons across sectors and episodes (high vs. low salience; concentrated vs. diffuse interests; crisis vs. non-crisis periods) and then extended across countries with similar institutional forms (e.g., late agencification; contested credibility; distributive exposure) to probe external validity (Jordana and Levi-Faur 2004; Gilardi 2002). The typology is compatible with mixed-method designs: qualitative process tracing can specify activation sequences (trigger → venue → coalition → instrument), while event-history or count models can code the incidence of activation by modality across time and sectors (Gilardi 2005).

Finally, the typology invites a normative question that is explicitly comparative: not whether “political interference” exists, but under what conditions legislative intervention serves democratic accountability rather than a channel for concentrated power. By separating modalities, specifying activation mechanisms, and identifying beneficiaries, comparative research can move beyond generic prescriptions about autonomy and evaluate institutional arrangements that best balance technical

capacity, legality, and representative control under different political-economic constraints (McCubbins et al. 1987; Dubash and Morgan 2013; Osorio 2014).

4.5 | Synthesis: Strategic Selectivity and Dependent Capitalism

Taken together, these episodes point to a broader conclusion. In dependent capitalism, legislative control over rulemaking is not an external interruption of an otherwise autonomous technocracy; it is one of the institutional mechanisms through which strategic selectivity is reasserted. Material, procedural, and ex post controls differ in timing and instrument, but all become salient when distributive conflict, legitimacy stress, and credibility pressures make insulated rulemaking politically costly. The value of the typology lies precisely in showing how these interventions remain institutionally distinct while responding to a common political problem.

5 | Conclusions and Implications for Democratic Accountability

The Brazilian evidence examined here shows that legislative control over agency rulemaking operates through three analytically distinct modalities: material redesign of delegated authority, procedural structuring of decision-making, and ex post review with sanctioning potential. The contribution is not limited to naming these modalities. By reconstructing triggers, arenas, coalitions, instruments, and regulatory consequences, the article shows that oversight is politically activated and that agency autonomy is exercised within a legislatively delimited field.

The theoretical contribution lies in specifying how mainstream oversight scholarship can be extended rather than rejected. Principal-agent and delegation models identify the available instruments of control, but they do not fully explain why particular interventions become salient at particular moments. That question requires endogenizing the principal. In the Brazilian case, legislative activation is shaped by coalition conflict, by the selective character of state institutions, and by the double pressure of dependent capitalism: the need to preserve external credibility while managing domestic distributive and legitimacy tensions.

This also has a comparative implication. Because the typology disaggregates “interference” into observable modalities and ties activation to identifiable political sequences, it offers a workable basis for theory-building comparison across regulatory states, even where exhaustive inventories of interventions are unavailable. It allows comparison without assuming that insulation is the norm and politics the exception. It also clarifies a normative point: legislative intervention is not democratically valuable or harmful in the abstract; its meaning depends on modality, beneficiary structure, and the kinds of interests it stabilizes or displaces.

From this perspective, the central question is not whether agencies should be insulated from politics altogether, but how institutional design can combine technical capacity with accountable forms of political correction. More precise statutory delegations, procedurally meaningful participation, legality-bound ex post

review, and lower asymmetries between organized sectors and diffuse publics do not eliminate the structural tensions diagnosed here, but they can narrow the space for capture and opportunism. A critical analysis of the State does not negate reform; it indicates the limits within which reform can be made realistic.

Taken together, the argument offers both an explanation of Brazilian legislative control and a framework for comparative research on regulatory states in the Global South. Agency autonomy, on this view, is neither original nor apolitical. Democratic accountability in peripheral regulatory states is better understood through the contested institutional forms in which technical rulemaking, political correction, and distributive conflict are continuously recomposed than through the expectation of pure insulation.

Author Contributions

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Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

No new data were generated in this study. The public sources analyzed (legislation, meeting minutes, and administrative documents) are available from the official websites cited in the references.

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